

DMP for Use case 8 – Water Detection

Version : v3 - 13 September 2024

This Data Management Plan aims to provide a brief description of the model and datasets associated with use case 8 – Water detection.

DMP Authors/Contacts

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Main stakeholder: INBO (An Leyssen)

DMP Language

English

1 Brief description of the use case

1.1 What needs to be monitored?

To address the historical lack of data on standing waters and support the Blue Deal's climate adaptation goals, this project monitors both permanent and temporary water surfaces in Flanders to enable an automated, high-frequency update of the official Watervlakken (Water Surfaces) map layer. Monitoring includes identifying the appearance of new water bodies and the disappearance of existing ones through change detection, as well as the precise delineation of water boundaries via object segmentation. Furthermore, the system is designed to identify (water-retaining depressions by detecting stagnant water presence following specific meteorological events. Delineating these temporary features, particularly in agricultural areas, is critical for identifying target zones for infiltration pools to combat drought and improve nutrient and carbon management.

1.2 Where should it be monitored?

Flanders

1.3 How often should it be monitored?

Permanent waters yearly (based on monthly seasonality), temporary waters as frequent as possible.

2 Modeling approach

2.1 What type of deep learning problem?

Image Segmentation: Marks the presence of an object through pixel-wise masks generated for each object in the image

2.2 Which model type(s) were used?

Whereas rule-based approaches and spectral indices have long been preferred for water segmentation on satellite imagery, machine learning models have gained attention throughout the past years. Convolutional neural networks are particularly suited to detect water surfaces in all their conditions and shapes. This was demonstrated amongst others by Yu et al. (2017), who combined a CNN with a logistic regression, Isikdogan, Bovik and Passalacqua (2017) and Chen (2018). Wieland et al. (2019) used a U-Net to distinguish water from clouds, shadows, snow/ice and land on Landsat TM, ETM+, OLI and Sentinel-2 images. Mateo Garcia et al. (2021) used both a simple CNN comprising four

convolutional layers and a U-Net for flood detection on Sentinel-2 imagery and reported similar accuracies for both architectures. Based on the results of the latter two studies, the U-Net architecture is used here.

3 Data

3.1 Description of the input data

The input data consists of a multimodal fusion of **Sentinel-1 SAR and Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery** to ensure consistent detection regardless of cloud cover. The primary sources are Sentinel-1A (providing C-band SAR data in VV and VH polarizations) and Sentinel-2 (2A and 2B) MSI sensors, with input features specifically focusing on six spectral bands (B2, B3, B4, B8, B11, and B12) and two radar polarizations. To capture dynamic surface water, these are used as single acquisitions with a strict temporal constraint of less than a 24-hour difference in acquisition time between the two sensors.

3.2 Description of the output data

4 Dataset 1

Dataset name or title: Watervlakken-maand_Sxxx_Syyy_2023-MM-DD

xxx and yyy refer to the geographical subdivision into three subsections: S001-S004, S005-S009 and S010-S013.

MM-DD are the month and day of the predictions, the day is always set to 01.

Dataset abstract:

This dataset provides high-resolution (20m) raster layers characterizing water presence each month across Flanders, Belgium. Developed within the framework of the GEO.INFORMED project, the data supports the monitoring of European Union water monitoring services.

Dataset locator: on INBO Google Drive under PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Outputs > Processed outputs > Watervlakken > *DATE* >

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

lisa.landuyt@vito.be

<https://geo-informed.be/>

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

ils.reusen@vito.be

Data format: .tif (geotiff)

Geometry: Raster

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG:3857 - WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator

Geographic bounding box (WGS84): outline of Flanders

Temporal extent: 2023

Date of last revision: 30/09/2024

Lineage: Derived from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 individual images with a UDF described in the associated workflow documentation.

Bands: 2 bands with prediction probability, one for Water (band1) and one for Land (band2)

Quality flags: none

Size of the dataset: 2.2 GB (per monthly output)

Accessibility: Available on request from Lisa Landuyt or IIs Reusen

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Output rasters are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) 'PRJ_GEO.INFORMED' and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files? No

4.1 Description of the reference data

Several external datasets are identified (Dataset 1-3). However, these are all static while surface water has a dynamic character. This could cause a disagreement between ground truth and input data and bias the training. Dataset 1 is the starting point of the main end user but does not encompass rivers, channels and artificial surface waters. Given these shortcomings, a reference dataset that is aligned with Sentinel-2 image acquisitions is created (Dataset 4) through manual checks and annotations based on Dataset 1-3 and very high resolution aerial imagery and Sentinel-2 satellite imagery.

4.1.1 Dataset 1

Dataset name or title:

INBO watervlakken

Dataset abstract:

The INBO Watervlakken dataset v1.1 is a gerefereerd dataset of all 'closed' permanent water bodies, so excluding rivers and channels. It was constructed based on topographic layers, aerial orthofoto imagery, a digital terrain model and field observations. The dataset comprises 88.713 polygons with areas ranging between 1.5 m² and 2.46 km².

For all details, see: Leyssen A., Scheers K., Smeekens V., Wils C., Packet J., De Knijf G. & Denys L. (2020). Watervlakken versie 1.1: polygonenkaart van stilstaand water in Vlaanderen. Uitgave 2020. Rapporten van het Instituut voor Natuur- en Bosonderzoek 2020 (40). Instituut voor Natuur- en Bosonderzoek, Brussel. DOI: doi.org/10.21436/inbor.19088385

Dataset locator:

<https://www.geopunt.be/catalogus/datasetfolder/61c4245b-a177-4fe8-a5cc-455475d7b40f>

Resource language:

Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

Team Zoetwater, INBO (watervlakken@inbo.be)

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

An Leyssen, INBO

Data format:

.shp

Geometry:

Polygons

Coordinate reference system (CRS):

Lambert72 (EPSG:31370)

Geographic bounding box:

westBoundLongitude: 22 546.57

eastBoundLongitude: 258 423.52

southBoundLatitude: 153 471.98

northBoundLatitude: 243 882.10

Temporal extent:

No timestamps. First version released in 2018 based on the GRB dataset (version 2014) and aerial imagery from 2015-2017.

Date of last revision:

Last partial revision (V1.2) was released in 2022, considering aerial imagery from 2019-2021.

Lineage:

Version available on geopunt.be is the official version.

Attributes:

- **WVLC:** *unique identification code of each water body*
- **WTRLICHC:** *code of the corresponding Flemish or local water body*
- **HYLAC:** *code according to Hyla*

- **NAAM:** name of water body
- **GEBIED:** name of the area in which the water body is situated
- **KRWTYPE:** (closest) Flemisch water type (see Leyssen et al. (2020) for full list of options)
- **KRWYPES:** status of water type
- **DIEPKL:** maximal depth of water body
- **CONNECT:** connectivity (one of: geïsoleerd, permanent, periodiek)
- **PEILBEHEER:** water level management (one of: instroom geregeld, afvoer geregeld, aan- en afvoer geregeld, geen peilbeheer)
- **FUNCTIE:** usage of water body (see Leyssen et al. (2020) for full list of options)
- **OPPWVL:** area of water body (m²)
- **OMTWVL:** perimeter of water body (m)

Quality flags (if available):

-

Number of samples in the dataset: for rasters = number of valid raster cells

93,135

Size of the dataset (MB):

100 MB (shapefile + ancillary files)

Screenshot of attribute table: FIGURE(S)

	WVLIC	WTRLIJCH	HYLAC	NAAM	GEBIED	KRWTYPER	KRWTYPES	DIEPKL	CONNECT	FUNCTIE	OPWWVL	OMTWVL
1	ANTBRM0001	NULL	0	Zwaluwenpoel	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	111,05437770400	52,85056556010
2	ANTBRM0002	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1679,00317618...	165,18152245700
3	ANTBRM0003	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	2633,66529617...	231,64986452900
4	ANTBRM0004	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	525,06172283800	156,14943346600
5	ANTBRM0005	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	408,70409308300	80,00995358710
6	ANTBRM0006	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	662,71769384100	121,37154608600
7	ANTBRM0007	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	2401,68411274...	269,12027541600
8	ANTBRM0008	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	3940,18036362...	274,21059087600
9	ANTBRM0009	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	146,10357933000	46,22950514160
10	ANTBRM0010	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	3401,90574455...	251,22685956900
11	ANTBRM0011	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	174,53708510300	57,97318629770
12	ANTBRM0012	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	802,01946253400	114,20724712400
13	ANTBRM0013	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1354,89880714...	153,22953224100
14	ANTBRM0014	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1796,16137736...	211,87785621500
15	ANTBRM0015	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	96,35345252370	36,32352408370
16	ANTBRM0016	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	105,79502405600	38,86429795270
17	ANTBRM0017	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	280,92890471200	78,81571499310
18	ANTBRM0018	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	573,57925458600	98,96295858540
19	ANTBRM0019	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	234,78843137200	79,95916343780
20	ANTBRM0020	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	6103,74272734...	366,25567005800
21	ANTBRM0021	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	133,54960399100	46,66369005560
22	ANTBRM0022	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	308,72193995200	79,80889378230
23	ANTBRM0023	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	357,50772234400	86,91226924740
24	ANTBRM0024	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	204,49079942300	72,02692772300
25	ANTBRM0025	NULL	0	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	3287,80637624...	319,07077972600

Screenshot of geometry (subpart): FIGURE(S)

Accessibility:

Publicly available online.

License (if applicable):

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Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any)

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How and when will the data be made publicly available? (If this is not yet the case)

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How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

Accompanying report: Scheers et al. (2022)

4.1.2 Dataset 2

Dataset name or title:

GRB Wtz

Dataset abstract:

The GRB, abbreviation of Grootchalig Referentiebestand in Dutch, is a geographic dataset comprising many features of the Flemish territory, including buildings, roads, rail tracks, water courses, the road network and parcels. All features have a scale between 1/250 en 1/5000. It is a common topographic reference for users of many different entities, and is used amongst others to look up addresses and parcels, as base map for visualizations, input for spatial analyses etc.

The Wtz layer/entity in the GRB dataset comprises all areas dominated by the physical presence of surface water, so both water courses and water bodies.

Dataset locator:

WMS layer: <https://geoservices.informatievlaanderen.be/raadpleegdiensten/GRB/wms>

Download

link:

<https://www.geopunt.be/catalogus/datasetfolder/7c823055-7bbf-4d62-b55e-f85c30d53162>

Resource language:

Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

Digital Flanders (digitaal.vlaanderen@vlaanderen.be)

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

Digital Flanders (digitaal.vlaanderen@vlaanderen.be)

Data format:

.shp

Geometry:

polygons

Coordinate reference system (CRS):

Lambert72 (EPSG:31370)

Geographic bounding box:

westBoundLongitude: 22546.98

eastBoundLongitude: 258481.62

southBoundLatitude: 153057.25

northBoundLatitude: 243917.64

Temporal extent:

2014 - now

Date of last revision:

Version 01-01-2022.

Lineage:

Dataset is updated regularly. Difference files can be downloaded to check which features changed, appeared or disappeared. Also, several attributes provide information on the history of a feature.

Attributes: short description of each attribute, with units and (link to) measurement protocol (if available)

- **OIDN:** *object identifier*
- **UIDN:** *version identifier*
- **VERSIE:** *version number*
- **BEGINDATUM:** *date the object was entered in the dataset*
- **VERSDATUM:** *date on which the object was last revised*
- **VHAG:** *identifier of the VHA-segment to which the object belongs*
- **NAAM:** *name of the VHA segment*
- **OPNDATUM:** *delivery date*
- **BGNINV:** *type of inventory task which led to the definition of update of the object*
- **LBLBGNINV:** *short description of inventory task*
- **LENGTE:** *perimeter length (m)*
- **OPPERVL:** *area (m²)*

Quality flags (if available):

-

Number of samples in the dataset: for rasters = number of valid raster cells

210,228

Size of the dataset (MB):

270 MB (shapefile + ancillary files)

Screenshot of attribute table: FIGURE(S)

	OIDN	LIJDN	VERSIE	BEGINDATUM	VERSDATUM	VHAG	NAAM	OPNDATUM	BGNINNV	LBLBGNINNV	LENGTE	OPPERVL
1	46731	65439	2	2010-04-06	2010-08-21	-9	nvt	2008-12-09	1	GRB aanmaak	454,41	4674,20
2	53711	69454	2	2010-06-03	2010-08-22	-9	nvt	2009-10-26	1	GRB aanmaak	229,78	3254,55
3	87859	100257	1	2011-05-09	2011-05-09	-9	nvt	2010-12-06	1	GRB aanmaak	59,86	278,88
4	89198	230847	2	2011-05-25	2016-12-03	-9	nvt	2011-01-28	11	adupdate	196,34	390,16
5	70397	82618	1	2010-11-05	2010-11-05	-9	nvt	2009-12-17	1	GRB aanmaak	160,45	365,67
6	69224	81445	1	2010-11-04	2010-11-04	-9	nvt	2010-07-05	1	GRB aanmaak	43,43	61,11
7	52772	234933	3	2010-05-31	2017-01-12	3262	Galgenbeek	2009-02-19	10	lokale bijhoudi...	82,78	141,11
8	112094	124797	1	2012-03-05	2012-03-05	8520	Vieminkloop	2011-05-13	1	GRB aanmaak	39,94	61,38
9	108998	121628	1	2012-01-17	2012-01-17	727	Biestwatergang	2011-09-19	1	GRB aanmaak	168,07	383,25
10	608	608	1	2005-05-26	2005-05-26	-9	nvt	2001-01-19	1	GRB aanmaak	110,72	658,83
11	52167	67386	2	2010-05-17	2010-08-21	-9	nvt	2009-10-09	1	GRB aanmaak	25,02	37,32
12	61888	63553	1	2010-08-18	2010-08-18	-9	nvt	2009-01-16	1	GRB aanmaak	92,68	664,17
13	33464	33778	1	2009-07-13	2009-07-13	104	nvt	2008-05-09	1	GRB aanmaak	100,62	228,81
14	68138	80359	1	2010-11-03	2010-11-03	-9	nvt	2010-02-22	1	GRB aanmaak	91,95	215,64
15	30538	30842	1	2009-05-15	2009-05-15	-9	nvt	2009-04-15	-8	niet gekend	9,04	5,15
16	84561	96946	1	2011-04-04	2011-04-04	-9	nvt	2010-06-30	1	GRB aanmaak	56,61	228,26
17	102825	115359	1	2011-10-05	2011-10-05	-8	ng	2011-07-04	1	GRB aanmaak	5,23	1,16
18	4434	181868	2	2006-11-17	2013-12-11	7169	Golmeerzouw...	2013-11-11	3	terreinupdate	60,49	96,31
19	71128	83349	1	2010-11-08	2010-11-08	-9	nvt	2010-02-15	1	GRB aanmaak	35,57	59,16
20	388	388	1	2005-05-26	2005-05-26	-9	nvt	2001-10-03	1	GRB aanmaak	46,03	115,35
21	66267	78379	2	2010-10-22	2010-10-25	169	Kapellebeek	2009-09-02	1	GRB aanmaak	178,29	314,47
22	98020	110527	1	2011-08-10	2011-08-10	-9	nvt	2011-03-01	1	GRB aanmaak	100,69	636,71
23	1163	218760	2	2006-01-25	2016-07-08	-9	nvt	2016-05-11	4	bijhouding binn...	377,73	6800,49
24	52270	67577	2	2010-05-17	2010-08-21	-9	nvt	2009-06-26	1	GRB aanmaak	100,87	223,46
25	107509	120116	1	2011-12-20	2011-12-20	6867	Dille Vierde Arm	2011-01-20	1	GRB aanmaak	132,90	535,93

Screenshot of geometry (subpart): FIGURE(S)

Accessibility:

Publicly available online

License (if applicable):

Gratis Open Data Licentie Vlaanderen v. 1.02

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any)

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How and when will the data be made publicly available? (If this is not yet the case)

-

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

-

4.1.3 Dataset 3

Dataset name or title: (Short) name or title of the dataset

OSM water

Dataset abstract:

OpenStreetMap (OSM) is a free, open geographic database updated and maintained by a community of volunteers via open collaboration. The dataset contains four core elements: nodes (points, e.g. points of interest or mountain peaks), ways (polylines or polygons, e.g. streets, rivers, forests, parks, lakes), relations (ordered lists of nodes, ways and relations, e.g. restrictions on roads, areas with holes) and tags (key-value pairs that store metadata on map objects).

As this dataset contains much more than rivers and lakes, a subset was created by selecting only the water polygon layer (code 82xx).

Dataset locator:

WMS layer: <https://tile.openstreetmap.org/%7bz%7d/%7bx%7d/%7by%7d.png>

Download: <https://download.geofabrik.de/> or through QGIS OSM plugin

Resource language: It refers to the language(s) used within the dataset

English

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

-

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

OSM team (support@openstreetmap.org)

Data format:

.shp

Geometry:

Polygons

Coordinate reference system (CRS):

WGS84 (EPSG:4326)

Geographic bounding box:

westBoundLongitude: 2.3623854000000000

eastBoundLongitude: 6.3871764999999998

southBoundLatitude: 49.5086640000000031

northBoundLatitude: 51.5051847000000009

Temporal extent:

Frequent updates but no explicit versioning.

Date of last revision:

Dataset used within the project context was downloaded on 14/02/2022.

Lineage:

Quality assurance is accomplished by both automated rule-based checks as well as expert interference (https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Quality_assurance).

Attributes: short description of each attribute, with units and (link to) measurement protocol (if available)

- **Osm_id:** *water body ID*
- **Code:** *water body class code*
- **Fclass:** *water body class*
- **Name:** *name of water body*

Quality flags (if available):

-

Number of samples in the dataset: for rasters = number of valid raster cells

66,510

Size of the dataset (MB):

40 MB (Flanders)

Screenshot of attribute table: FIGURE(S)

osm_id	code	fclass	name
1	3993437	8200 water	Vijver van Oud...
2	3993438	8200 water	NULL
3	3993454	8200 water	NULL
4	3994323	8201 reservoir	NULL
5	3994324	8201 reservoir	NULL
6	3994325	8201 reservoir	NULL
7	4003917	8200 water	NULL
8	4112046	8200 water	NULL
9	4309315	8200 water	Galgenweel
10	4319263	8200 water	NULL
11	4322795	8200 water	Kempisch dok
12	4322795	8203 dock	Kempisch dok
13	4322820	8200 water	Asiadok
14	4322820	8203 dock	Asiadok
15	4322840	8200 water	Houtdok
16	4323234	8200 water	Grote Put
17	4323235	8200 water	Kleine Put
18	4326384	8200 water	Bevrijdingsdok
19	4326384	8203 dock	Bevrijdingsdok
20	4327092	8200 water	NULL
21	4327158	8200 water	NULL
22	4327206	8200 water	Kanaaldok B3
23	4327206	8203 dock	Kanaaldok B3
24	4328365	8200 water	Bonapartedok
25	4328365	8203 dock	Bonapartedok

Screenshot of geometry (subpart): FIGURE(S)

Accessibility:

Publicly available online

License (if applicable):

Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL)

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any)

-

How and when will the data be made publicly available? (If this is not yet the case)

-

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

-

4.1.4 Dataset 4

Dataset name or title: (Short) name or title of the dataset

VITO annotations

Dataset abstract:

This dataset comprises manually digitized polygons across 7 AOIs in Flanders. The annotations were performed based on aerial orthophoto imagery (if coinciding), Sentinel-2 satellite imagery, topographical information and datasets 1-3. They represent snapshots of the water bodies at considered Sentinel-2 acquisition times. Polygons are aligned with the coinciding Sentinel-2 image if a displacement is present.

Dataset locator:

Data available on request.

Resource language: It refers to the language(s) used within the dataset

English

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

VITO Remote Sensing (Lisa.Landuyt@vito.be)

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

VITO Remote Sensing (Lisa.Landuyt@vito.be)

Data format:

.shp

Geometry:

Polygons

Coordinate reference system (CRS): WGS84, Lambert72, ...

Lambert72 (EPSG:31370)

Geographic bounding box [west, south, east, north]:

- AOI1: [145660.29, 187721.46, 161655.29, 201425.38]
- AOI2: [647021.63, 5643593.38, 657206.09, 5651112.36]
- AOI3: [196901.21, 198443.01, 209097.13, 223897.91]
- AOI4: [233702.27, 191710.79, 249142.85, 209279.99]
- AOI5: [691864.85, 5654479.65, 694803.29, 5656948.14]
- AOI6: [486518.57, 5647960.32, 491504.69, 5651018.80]
- AOI7: [45218.37, 169561.57, 50712.49, 172682.38]

Temporal extent: The temporal extent defines the time period covered by the content of the resource. This time period may be expressed as an individual date, an interval of dates (starting date and ending date) or a mix of individual dates and intervals of dates.

AOI1	AOI2	AOI3	AOI4	AOI5	AOI6	AOI7
24/02/2018	24/02/2018	27/03/2017	24/02/2018	24/02/2018	25/02/2018	06/05/2017
01/04/2019	30/06/2018	25/02/2018	27/03/2020	27/03/2020	15/07/2018	25/02/2018
21/02/2021	01/04/2019	27/06/2018	06/03/2021	06/03/2021	26/03/2020	26/03/2020
28/11/2020	17/03/2020	21/07/2021	16/01/2020		31/03/2021	31/03/2021
27/04/2020		05/05/2020	18/04/2019			14/06/2021
02/06/2017		29/08/2017	30/05/2021			02/08/2018
06/08/2018		14/09/2020	15/07/2018			16/10/2018
17/09/2020		24/10/2021	14/09/2020			22/11/2017
22/11/2019		04/12/2019	09/10/2021			25/07/2019
12/12/2018		21/01/2019	21/12/2021			14/01/2019

Date of last revision:

Last revision: 12/05/2022

Lineage:

Quality assurance to be performed, no legal validity.

Attributes: short description of each attribute, with units and (link to) measurement protocol (if available)

- *(If geometry from INBO or GRB dataset, attributes from that dataset are copied)*

- *Type: type of water body (waterlichaam, waterlichaam-zw for pools, waterlichaam-in for industrial water surfaces)*
- *Vegetation: 1 if water surface is covered by vegetation*
- *Temporary: 1 if water surface is temporary*
- *Saturation: 1 if water presence very shallow / soil is saturated*
- *Shallow: 1 if water depth is shallow*
- *Trees: 1 if water surface is covered by trees*
- *Invisible: 1 if water surface is not visible on Sentinel-2 imagery*
- *Uncertain: 1 if water presence and/or boundaries are uncertain*
- *Source: source of polygon shape: VITO, GRB, OSM or VITO*

Quality flags (if available):

Column “uncertain” equals 1 of polygon class and/or shape are uncertain.

Number of samples in the dataset: for rasters = number of valid raster cells

AOI1	AOI2	AOI3	AOI4	AOI5	AOI6	AOI7
02/06/2017: 771	24/02/2018: 385	27/03/2017: 712	24/02/2018: 200	24/02/2018: 43	25/02/2018: 217	06/05/2017: 217
24/02/2018: 784	30/06/2018: 367	29/08/2017: 705	15/07/2018: 217	27/03/2020: 55	15/07/2018: 160	22/11/2017: 213
06/08/2018: 785	01/04/2019: 380	25/02/2018: 716	18/04/2019: 205	06/03/2021: 62	26/03/2020: 261	25/02/2018: 217
12/12/2018: 780	17/03/2020: 641	27/06/2018: 711	16/01/2020: 205		31/03/2021: 195	02/08/2018: 211
01/04/2019: 787		21/01/2019: 709	27/03/2020: 217			16/10/2018: 212
22/11/2019: 789		04/12/2019: 708	14/09/2020: 210			14/01/2019: 215
27/04/2020: 795		05/05/2020: 716	06/03/2021: 227			25/07/2019: 210
17/09/2020: 794		14/09/2020: 724	30/05/2021: 211			26/03/2020: 214
28/11/2020: 792		21/07/2021: 733	09/10/2021: 210			31/03/2021: 217
21/02/2021: 794		24/10/2021: 722	21/12/2021: 215			14/06/2021: 215

Size of the dataset (MB):

28.3 MB

Screenshot of attribute table: FIGURE(S)

AOI1_water_2021-02-21 — Features Total: 794, Filtered: 794, Selected: 0

KRWTTYPES	DIEPKL	CONNECT	FUNCTIE	OPPWVL	OMTWVL	type	vegetation	temporary	saturation	shallow	trees	invisible	uncertain	source
1	NULL	NULL	NULL	14750.3728618...	1246.45960188...	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	INBO
2	NULL	NULL	NULL	140.24595849600	58.04293863950	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	INBO
3	NULL	NULL	NULL	6391.11748798...	385.63037945200	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	INBO
4	NULL	NULL	NULL	14117.20122291...	634.63133183800	Waterlichaam	NULL	1	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	INBO
5	NULL	NULL	NULL	40.40600512830	40.85179611230	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	INBO
6	NULL	NULL	NULL	2046.30178204...	177.39309822200	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	INBO
7	NULL	NULL	NULL	136.55079201300	48.02166828350	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	INBO
8	NULL	NULL	NULL	511.29276946300	90.31121969520	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	1	NULL	INBO
9	NULL	NULL	NULL	1937.18600135...	302.51709806500	Waterlichaam	NULL	1	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	1	INBO
10	NULL	NULL	NULL	135.30001123300	47.89060824170	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	1	1	INBO
11	NULL	NULL	NULL	101.25239689800	37.21816381970	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	NULL	INBO
12	NULL	NULL	NULL	1835.75194456...	205.29470823900	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	NULL	NULL	INBO
13	NULL	NULL	NULL	381.90195401000	81.49581718940	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	INBO
14	NULL	NULL	NULL	1795.67049056...	162.87719784100	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	INBO
15	NULL	NULL	NULL	31.64478801370	28.28124623810	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	1	INBO
16	NULL	NULL	NULL	233.69761058200	61.58797544670	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	NULL	INBO
17	NULL	NULL	NULL	655.52009645900	114.77181710100	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	INBO
18	NULL	NULL	NULL	316.49168962600	78.26484261230	Waterlichaam	NULL	1	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	INBO
19	NULL	NULL	NULL	849.88053071000	106.80217873100	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	1	NULL	INBO
20	NULL	NULL	NULL	176.61806894300	60.74752691900	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	NULL	INBO
21	NULL	NULL	NULL	5736.90490485...	297.84511005700	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	INBO
22	NULL	NULL	NULL	133.05705959300	101.99156045600	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	NULL	INBO
23	NULL	NULL	NULL	3718.93827954...	781.50658518500	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	1	1	NULL	INBO
24	NULL	NULL	NULL	4772.73376447...	341.02180781400	Waterlichaam	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	NULL	INBO

Show All Features

Screenshot of geometry (subpart): FIGURE(S)

Accessibility:

Available on request (Lisa.Landuyt@vito.be)

License (if applicable):

-

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any)

-

How and when will the data be made publicly available? (If this is not yet the case)

-

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?

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